

D3.6 PRODUCTION OF PE PCR PELLETS WITH A QUALITY OF OVER 0.9 RELATED TO PROCESSING AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES COMPARED TO VIRGIN PELLETS & EXTRUDER TRIAL

WORK PACKAGE 3

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
AO	Antioxidant
BFE	Blow-film extruding
C	Compounded
CE	Cast extrusion
CO	Coperion twin screw extruder
DSC	Differential scanning calorimetry
DB	Dry blend
EBM	Extrusion blow molding
IM	Injection molding
KM	Krauss Maffei twin screw extruder
LCA	Life cycle analysis
LDPE	Low density polyethylene
L/D	Length over diameter
MD	Machine direction
MFI	Melt flow index
MFR	Melt flow rate
MVR	Melt volume rate
NAO	Without Antioxidant
OIT	Oxygen induction time
OTR	Oxygen transmission rate
PCR	Post-consumer recycled
PE	Polyethylene
QMRP	Quality model for recycled plastic
RPM	Rounds per minute
RQ	Recyclate quality
TDS	Technical data sheet
TSE	Twin-screw extruder
WVTR	Water vapor transmission rate

PUBLISHABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is related to **Task 3.5: Mechanical recycling tests and application development**. In this task, recyclates coming from the various Loops in the projects are compounded to granulates, ready for conversion into new products. A target was set to obtain recycled granulates with a quality value over 0.9 (on a scale 0-1). Furthermore, it was part of this task to assess how representative results from lab compounding can be for (semi) industrial compounding.

We have therefore split the deliverable into two main parts as follows:

RecyQmeter:

This section assesses the quality of recycled products which are generated in this project using novel processes combinations such as using dissolution-based recycling or water-based deinking and delamination. The focus in this calculation has been on Loop3 (cycle1) materials. It uses a combination of two published quality models (Demets, 2021 and Golkaram, 2022). The results show that the recyclates are well-suited for blown film extrusion applications. Among those, the shrink and heavy-duty films are the best markets with quality value of around 0.94-0.95. However, the quality value for shrink film applications may vary because not all tests were conducted for this specific application. Instead, a general set of tests was conducted to assess the quality across various applications, leading to a higher deviation in the evaluated results.

Extruder trial:

In addition to the quality assessment of recycled products, an extruder trial was conducted on Loop2 materials. Since the size of an extruder significantly affects the shear rates experienced in the melt, it can influence homogenization and potential thermal degradation of the extruded plastic. An 18 mm co-rotating twin-screw extruder (TSE) at lab scale was compared with a 25mm co-rotating TSE at semi-industrial scale as part of an intermediate process preceding the actual industrial recycling step. Overall, while the 18 mm Coperion extruder exhibited decreased oxidative stability compared to the 25 mm Krauss-Maffei, no other substantial differences were observed in the tests conducted. This suggests that, aside from oxidative stability, both extruders perform comparably in the evaluated tests.

1. RECAP – THE DIFFERENT LOOPS IN THE PROJECT

The project addresses flexible household post-consumer packaging waste (PE-rich) from Germany, Belgium, and France, as well as Business-to-Business (B2B) collected coffee packaging waste, through demonstration in 3 Loop scenarios:

Loop 1 targets flexible packaging from real household waste, to show that an adapted cascade of pre-treatment, recycling and post-treatment technologies can improve the recyclate so that it can be reused in film applications for home care, or even personal care packaging.

Loop 2 investigates the potential of a closed loop business to business (B2B) collection of flexible packaging. The closed system and an adequate recycling cascade shall allow the recycled material to be used in food packaging again.

Loop 3 consists of two cycles to simulate the repeated use of recycled material in packaging and investigate the consequences of a second recycling step on the material properties. In this Loop 3 scenario, the tracer-based sorting (TBS) is applied to separate food from non-food packaging in the sorting step. Further, different recycling cascades are looked at in Work package 3 (WP3) and selected, so that the highest recyclate quality can be reached. The targeted application is food packaging for the tracer-based sorted food packaging input waste.

2. INTRODUCTION (RECYQMETER)

Mechanical recycling techniques comprise re-melting, melt-filtration and re-compounding. Plastic materials generated are mechanically recycled into ready-to-use granules for plastics converting industry. This involves conventional (re-)extrusion of pellets, however using specialized techniques for film recyclates, which includes densification of the fluffy materials according to current recycling processes for films, melt filtration and compounding with necessary additives or virgin PE whenever needed, which in this case can be considered a 'booster' component.

Granulates from WP3 in Task T3.4 produced by dissolution-based purification and in Task T3.3 by water based deinking purification and subsequent mechanical recycling were tested for the relevant physico-chemical and mechanical properties, as well as for their processability via (multi-layered) film blowing, injection molding or thermoforming, depending on their processing-related properties.

Based on the results, the recyclates are rated in UM's existing quality model for recycled plastics, which indicate how far the quality is from 'virgin' material on a scale from 0-1. Within CFP the ambition was to achieve a quality above 0.9 in this model (which typically allows closed loop recycling).

3. METHOD (RECYQMETER)

RecyQMeter uses a combination of two recently published models namely Quality Model for Recycled Plastic (QMRP) and Recyclate Quality (RQ) model [1, 2]. Building on the two methodologies, RecyQMeter uses three different groups of properties, namely processing (melt flow index (MFI), zero shear viscosity), material (tensile strength, modulus, impact strength, elongation at break, tear strength (film only)) and product properties (oxygen transmission rate (OTR), water vapor transmission rate (WVTR), odor, sealing properties, haze, gloss, regulatory properties). For each of these three property groups a quality value is reported. This quality value for individual properties is calculated as follows; a function is defined depending on the property of interest (e.g. tensile strength) which can be trapezoidal (double), bell-shaped, gaussian, trapezoidal (single), sigmoidal. For properties such as food contact regulations a go/no-go is applied where a threshold or specific migration limit is used as I_{max} . For Oxygen Transmission Rate (OTR), Water Vapor Transmission Rate (WVTR) and odor, the higher the value of the property the lower the quality. However, there is always an acceptable value below which the quality is constant and equal to 1.0. For other product related properties usually a double trapezoidal-shaped function is applied, while a single trapezoidal-shaped function is used for mechanical properties. The user does not have direct influence on the choice of function. But by choosing a property such as tensile strength, the tool calls the respective function defined per property from the database.

3.1 Aggregating quality values

To estimate the quality score:

$$\text{RecyQMeter score: } \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot f_i \quad , \sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1 \text{ (Eq. 1)}$$

where f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots represent the scoring functions for the different properties.

The user of the tool can choose a built-in go/no-go criterion indicating that if one of the quality scores (i.e: f_x) equals zero, the RecyQMeter score yields a zero as well no matter how well other properties perform.

3.2 Weighing factors

QMRP and RQ apply a weighting factor to emphasize the importance of the properties for different applications. For example, impact strength plays an important role in the application of plastics in toys (Golkaram et al. 2022). Thus far, these values have been estimated based on expert opinions in both models. The full list of weighting factors is presented in the Supporting Information. These values are based on interviews and questionnaires sent to the relevant industry experts.

4. RESULTS (RECYQMETER)

The quality of recycled films was analyzed and technical data sheets (TDS), were provided. Different properties were measured to characterize the recycled material regarding different aspects of quality. Table 1 and Table 2 show the result of characterizations for the 100% PE PCR based extruded films, PE PCRs produced by dissolution-based recycling and by water based deinking and mechanical recycling techniques, respectively. The input waste used for PE PCR production was the tracer-based-sorted post-consumer flexible food packaging (so-called Loop3/Cycle 1 material in the project).

Table 1: Loop3|cycle 1 thin sheet extrusion of PE PCRs with 100 % PCR (PE PCR production by dissolution based recycling techniques)

Property	Value	Unit
MFI (ISO 1133-1)	0.95	(g/10 min)
E modulus (ISO 527-3)	129	MPa
Strain at break (ISO 527-3)	616	%
Dart drop impact	2.78	(g/μm)
Yield strength (ISO 527-3)	9.4	MPa
Haze	11.7	%

Table 2: Loop3 cycle 1 thin sheet extrusion of PE PCRs with 100 % PCR (PE PCR production by water based deinking and mechanical recycling techniques)

Property	Value	Unit
MFI (ISO 1133-1)	0.94	(g/10 min)
E modulus (ISO 527-3)	127	MPa
Strain at break (ISO 527-3)	652	%
Dart drop impact	3.62	(g/μm)
Yield strength (ISO 527-3)	9.4	MPa
Haze	15.3	%

The quality of recyclates depend on different applications or markets. Using RecyQMeter, an automated tool for quality assessment of recycled plastic, the quality is estimated and shown in Table 3 and Table 4, respectively for the two different types of PE PCRs.

Table 3: Result of quality assessment using RecyQMeter. The quality of Loop3|cycle 1 thin sheet extrusion dissolution-based recycling 100 % PCR samples are estimated for different markets (IM: Injection moulding, BFE: blown film extrusion, EBM: extrusion blow moulding, CE: cast extrusion).

Processing technique	Application	Quality value
IM	Lid	0.7787
IM	pull tabs	0.787
IM	caps	0.7254
BFE	building and construction Film	0.6989
BFE	Green house film	0.9177
BFE	Mulch Film	0.8873
BFE	Industrial, heavy-duty bag	0.9253
BFE	Heavy duty sack	0.9446
BFE	shopping bag	0.9313
BFE	Shrink film	0.9462
BFE	Overwrap film	0.7285
BFE	Sealing layer in multilayer	0.8693
BFE	Collation shrink film	0.8463
BFE	shrink hood	0.9177
BFE	Lamination	0.9061
EBM	Squeezable bottles and ampules	0.7703
CE	Artificial turf	0.7887
CE	Silage film	0.536
CE	Geomembranes	0.8731
CE	Lamination/Coating -- extrusion coating	0.8
CE	Stretch wrap/hood	0.7785
IM	Containers, laundry baskets	0.7662
IM	Food storage containers/buckets (industrial)	0.7662
IM	Spouts/faucets	0.7761

Table 4: Result of quality assessment using RecyQMeter. The quality of Loop3|cycle 1 thin sheet extrusion 100 % PCR samples (PE PCR production by water based deinking and mechanical recycling techniques) are estimated for different markets. (IM: Injection molding, BFE: blown film extrusion, EBM: extrusion blow molding, CE: cast extrusion).

Processing technique	Application	Quality value
IM	Lid	0.7746
IM	pull tabs	0.7857
IM	caps	0.7289
BFE	building and construction Film	0.7081
BFE	Green house film	0.9515
BFE	Mulch Film	0.9186
BFE	Industrial, heavy duty bag	0.9232
BFE	Heavy duty sack	0.944
BFE	shopping bag	0.929
BFE	Shrink film	0.9438
BFE	Overwrap film	0.7344
BFE	Sealing layer in multilayer	0.8727
BFE	Collation shrink film	0.8499
BFE	shrink hood	0.8497
BFE	Lamination	0.9079
EBM	Squeezable bottles and ampules	0.7769
CE	Artificial turf	0.7955
CE	Silage film	0.4815
CE	Geomembranes	0.8935
CE	Lamination/Coating -- extrusion coating	0.8036
CE	Stretch wrap/hood	0.7983
IM	Containers, laundry baskets	0.762
IM	Food storage containers/buckets (industrial)	0.762

Table 1 shows the material properties for the sample 100 % PE PCR thin sheet extruded using PE PCRs, which are produced by means of dissolution-based recycling. Input waste was Loop3/Cycle 1 as described above. Using these values as the input to RecyQMeter, provides with a list of quality scores for a variety of applications listed in Table 3. Among all the markets, blown film extrusion products (BFE) show the best match. Among the BFE products, heavy duty and shrink films have the highest scores of up to 0.9462.

For the samples, 100 % PE PCR thin sheet extruded using PE PCRs, which are produced by means of water based deinking and mechanical recycling techniques, the outcome is similar; the shrink and heavy-duty films are the best match with the highest score of 0.944.

The values are relative to the technical data sheets of virgin plastic for that specific application. Let's take shrink film as an example. The model gave a score of 0.944 for the application based on the input properties. The data attached, shown in Table 5, includes the data supplier, the extracted properties, and a table summarizing the ideal values used in the tool for calculations. Note that some data differs from the supplier's values when transferred to the tool due to expert corrections, unit conversions, or normalization by thickness.

Table 5: RecyQmeter data base for shrink film applications

Process	Application	Sub-Application	Producer	Grade	MFR 190°C, 2.16kg	Film/ Tensile strength at Yield (MD) (Mpa)	Elongation at break (MD) (ASTM D882/ ISO	Modulus (Mpa) (MD)	Elmendorf tear strength MD (g/μm)	Tear Strength (N/mm)	Tear Resistance (g/micron) (MD)	Impact Strength , Dart Drop (g)	Gloss ASTM D2457 45o	Haze
Packaging	Film	Shrink Film	Dioki	OKITEN 222A	0.3	10.5	280			110			60	5
Packaging	Film	Shrink Film	Hanwha Group	HANW HA LDPE 5312P	0.5		240			107.9		120		9
Packaging	Film	Shrink Film	Hanwha Group	HANW HA LDPE 5301	0.3		350				11	250		16
Packaging	Film	Shrink Film	Hanwha Group	HANW HA LDPE 5316	0.8		280				11	100		8.5
Packaging	Film	Shrink Film	Versalis (Eni Group)	RIBLEN E FC 30	0.25	10	400	160		22		350	50	12
Packaging	Film	Shrink Film	Versalis (Eni Group)	RIBLEN E FF 20	0.8	10	450	165	40			250	70	8

Packaging	Film	Shrink Film	SABIC	LDPE HP4027 NN	4	11	256	270	10		10	30	72	5
Packaging	Film	Shrink Film	ExxonMobil	ENABLE 2305MI	0.5	11	480	240			70	170	52	9.3
Packaging	Film	Shrink Film	ExxonMobil	ENABLE 2005PA	0.5	9.9	480	210			90	240	57	7.8
Packaging	Film	Shrink Film	SABIC	LDPE HP4027 J	4	11	256	270			10	3	72	5
		MIN			0.25	9.9	240	160	10	22	10	3	50	5
		MAX			4	11	480	270	40	110	90	350	72	16

5. CONCLUSION (RECYQMETER)

It has been demonstrated that the recycling cascades developed in the CIRCULAR FoodPack project (specifically for Loop3-cycle 1 input waste materials) can produce recyclates with a quality factor exceeding 0.9. Values as high as 0.944 were achieved for targeted use in flexible PE applications, such as shrink and heavy-duty films.

The model-generated results, based on input values, may yield higher or lower scores for certain applications. This variation can occur when not all application-relevant tests are conducted, leading to missing data and greater deviations in assessing the quality of the recycled materials. To improve accuracy for example, in shrink films additional testing is required, such as Elmendorf Tear Strength (MD) (g/μm), Tear Strength (N/mm), and Tear Resistance (g/micron) (MD).

As an example, for the application of these PE PCRs in flexible food packaging, the quality factor is expected to be slightly less than 0.9. This is because their incorporation is only feasible with functional barriers developed during the project, based on the purity levels.

6. INTRODUCTION (EXTRUDER TRIAL)

The primary objective of work package (WP3) is to develop and implement recycling processes that enable the use of recyclates primarily in food-grade flexible packaging and in high-level applications such as home and personal care packaging. Task T3.5 more specifically targets mechanical recycling tests. Shredded and cleaned flakes are the input for re-melting, melt filtration and re-compounding. The subsequent characterization to indicate further processing steps are also considered as part of the task. For this deliverable 3.6, a so-called extruder trial is being set up. Since the size of an extruder significantly affects the shear rates experienced in the melt, eventually influencing homogenization and potential thermal degradation of the extruded plastic, an 18mm co-rotating TSE (lab scale) will be compared with a 25 mm co-rotating TSE (semi-industrial scale) as part of an intermediate process preceding the actual industrial recycling step. During the extruder trial, the various granules are characterized and processed to blown films. The obtained films also undergo various characterization tests. The conclusion of the extruder trial will give a more in-depth look at the effect of 'scaling up' the extruder size.

Figure 1: Schematic view of up scaling.

7. MATERIALS AND METHOD (EXTRUDER TRIAL)

The material used was provided by AMCOR-G and AMCOR-K. These were laminates (loop 2 input waste material) and antioxidant. The laminates are produced for Loop2: Waste input: 200 kg food flexible packaging controlled collected and delivered by NESTLE. Output: PE based mono-material laminate with PE virgin and PE PCR including the functional barriers, the laminate was produced by AMCOR-G and AMCOR-K. For the extruder trial the input material is used (PE based mono-material laminate) and an antioxidant was also used to enhance the stability of the material. The antioxidant (AO) used was Polybatch AO 25. In addition to the effect of the different extruders (lab scale and semi-industrial), various other factors were investigated, such as the influence of an extra thermal step or the addition of AO via compounding or dry blending. Table 6 provides an overview of the various factors of the samples, and Table 7 explains the sample names with descriptions.

Table 6: Overview of the various factors in the samples.

Sample identification	Antioxidant	Antioxidant compounded on	Extra thermal step
	Compounded/Dry blend	Coperion/KraussMaffei	Yes/No
F-KM-C	Compounded	KraussMaffei	No
F-CO-C	Not possible		
F-KM-DB	Dry blend	KraussMaffei	No
F-KM-KM-C	Compounded	KraussMaffei	Yes
F-KM-CO-C	Compounded	Coperion	Yes

Table 7: Sample names with descriptions.

Sample identification	Description
G-KM-AO	Granules compounded with a KraussMaffei with 5 wt% AO
G-KM-NAO	Granules compounded with a KraussMaffei without AO
G-KM-KM-AO	Granules compounded twice with a KraussMaffei, adding 5 wt% AO during the second step
G-KM-CO-AO	Granules compounded with a KraussMaffei then Coperion, adding 5wt% AO during the Coperion step
F-KM-C	Blown film from granules compounded with a KraussMaffei with 5 wt% AO
F-KM-DB	Blown film from granules compounded with KraussMaffei and dry-blended with 5 wt% AO after compounding
F-KM-KM-C	Blown film from granules compounded twice with a KraussMaffei, adding 5 wt% AO during the second step
F-KM-CO-C	Blown film from granules compounded with a KraussMaffei then Coperion, adding 5 wt% AO during the Coperion step

The laminates obtained from AMCOR were compounded with a 5 wt% (wt%: weight percent) antioxidant using two different TSE (twin-screw extruders): a KraussMaffei Wegmann ZE 25 (co-rotating, 52 L/D, Ø 25 mm) and a Coperion ZSK18 (co-rotating, 40 L/D, Ø 18 mm). The obtained granules were characterized by MFI, density, and OIT, and afterwards blown into film using a Brabender Kompaktextruder KE30 (single-screw extruder 19 L/D, Ø 25 mm). The blown films were characterized by tensile strength, haze, transparency, thickness and dart impact strength. Figure 1 shows a schematic overview of the various compounds and films produced during the extruder trial.

Figure 2: Schematic overview of the whole research.

7.1. Pre-processing

Before compounding, a shredding step was introduced to shred the laminates from a particle size of approximately 10mm to a particle size of approximately 6 mm. To achieve this particle size, a Hellweg (MDS 340/150) shredder (Figure 3) using a sieve with 6 mm openings was used. This resulted in laminates with a particle size of approximately 6 mm.

Figure 3: Hellweg (MDS 340/150) shredder

7.2. Compounding

The compounding was performed using two different twin-screw extruders: a KraussMaffei Wegmann ZE 25 (Figure 4) and a Coperion ZSK18 (Figure 5). The main differences between these extruders were the screw diameter (\varnothing 25 mm for KraussMaffei and \varnothing 18 mm for Coperion) and the length-to-diameter ratio (L/D) (52 L/D for KraussMaffei and 40 L/D for Coperion). Both twin-screw extruders had a universal screw build (see appendix 1). The compounding temperature was 210 °C, and a screw speed of 200 RPM was used for both twin-screw extruders.

KraussMaffei:

Compounding with the KraussMaffei was done at a temperature of 210 °C and a screw speed of 200 RPM. For the full temperature profile, see (Appendix II). The melt temperature during processing was 223 °C, and a die pressure of 41 bar was recorded. The total throughput was 8 kg/h, comprising 7.6 kg/h of laminates (95 %) and 0.4 kg/h of antioxidant (5 %). The compounding process proceeded smoothly without any issues.

Figure 4: KraussMaffei Wegmann ZE 25.

Coperion:

Direct compounding of laminates with antioxidant was not feasible using the Coperion extruder. The Coperion experienced difficulties in material feeding at high feed speeds, bridging occurred with the laminates, and at low speeds, precise dosing of the antioxidant at a 5 % ratio was unachievable. To resolve this, the laminates were first compounded on the KraussMaffei under the same process parameters and conditions but without the addition of antioxidant. Afterwards, the newly compounded laminates were then compounded with the antioxidant on the Coperion. Compounding on the KraussMaffei did not encounter any problems. Compounding with the Coperion was done at a temperature of 210 °C and a screw speed of 200 RPM. For the full temperature profile, see (Appendix III). The melt temperature during processing was 218 °C, and a die pressure of 52 bar was recorded. The total throughput was 4 kg/h, comprising 3.8 kg/h of laminates (95%) and 0.2 kg/h of antioxidant (5 %). The compounding process on the Coperion proceeded smoothly without any feeding issues or other problems.

Figure 5: Coperion ZSK 18.

7.3. Characterization of the pellets

The granules obtained after compounding with the two twin-screw extruders were characterized by their melt flow rate (MFR), volume flow rate (MVR), density and oxygen induction time (OIT). The MFR and MVR of the samples were assessed at 210 °C with a weight of 2.16 kg, according to ISO 1133 (Tinius Olsen MP1200). For density, the granules were characterized with a Mettler Toledo XSE105 DualRange analytical balance according to ISO 1183-1 in ethanol. The OIT was measured using a DSC from Mettler Toledo, at 210 °C and under an oxygen atmosphere. It is a measure of the material's stability in downstream processing.

7.4. Blown film extrusion

The different grades of compounded granules were processed in a single-screw extruder, the Brabender Kompaktextruder KE30 (single-screw extruder 19L/D, Ø 25 mm), with a screen changer and a blown film take-off unit. The processing temperature range was set from 170 to 210 °C, and an 80-mesh melt filter was used for all the different grades. The film blowing of the single-compounded granules (G-KM-C/G-KM-DB) went smoothly without any problems (Figure 6). However, for the granules that were compounded twice (G-KM-KM-C/G-KM-CO-C), there were issues when opting for a small thickness film. The major problem was that at small thicknesses, the bubbles burst due to impurities, making it impossible to maintain a stable process. To address this issue, a thicker film was produced by decreasing the take-off speed, preventing any bubble bursts, and ensuring a stable process.

Figure 6: Film blowing process of G-KM-C.

7.5. Characterization of the film

The blown films obtained from the various granule grades were assessed on their tensile strength (in the machine direction (MD)), transparency, haze, dart impact strength and OIT. The tensile properties of the films were assessed according to ISO 527-3 (Instron 5565). The initial grip separation was set to 100 mm, and the rate of grip separation used was rate 1, 1mm/min and rate 2, 50 mm/min. The test specimens used showed dimensions of ca. 20 mm width and ca. 140 mm (length). The strain was defined from the position of the crosshead, and initial gauge length was 100 mm. The transparency and haze of the films were evaluated using the transmittance mode and the illuminant D65/10 (HunterLab, model UltraScan PRO Spectrophotometer). The thickness was evaluated by measuring the films multiple times (min. 10x), in the central part of their width and along their length, using a thickness gauge (Mitutoyo, model 7327A, resolution of 0.001 mm). The dart impact tests were characterized according to ASTM D709 with a dart weight of 55.0 g with additional weights.

8. RESULTS (EXTRUDER TRIAL)

8.1. Characterization results of the pellets

The granules obtained after twin screw compounding of the laminates with the Antioxidant were characterized for their MFR and MVR (Table 8), Density (Table 9) and OIT (Table 10).

Table 8: MFR and MVR of the compounded samples (granulates) at 210 °C, 2.16 kg.

Sample	MFR (g/10 min)		MVR (cm ³ /10 min)	
	Mean	St. Dev.	Mean	St. Dev.
G-KM-AO	0.763	0.012	0.992	0.016
G-KM-NAO	0.724	0.013	0.857	0.015
G-KM-KM-AO	0.861	0.011	1.019	0.013
G-KM-CO-AO	0.866	0.016	1.025	0.019

The MFR and MVR results were generated according to the method prescribed in Chapter 7.3, *Characterization of the Pellets*. All the samples showed low MFR/MVR values, indicating that the viscosity is high. However, for the samples G-KM-KM-AO and G-KM-CO-AO, the MFR/MVR values were higher. This is the result of an extra thermal step applying extra shear stress, thus degrading the sample more, resulting in a lower viscosity than the samples that were extruded once.

Table 9: Density of the compounded samples (granulates).

Sample	Density (g/cm ³)	
	Mean	St. Dev.
G-KM-AO	0.938	0.001
G-KM-NAO	0.938	0.001
G-KM-KM-AO	0.939	0.001
G-KM-CO-AO	0.932	0.002

The density results were generated according to the method prescribed in Chapter 6.3, *Characterization of the Pellets*. In the density results from the granules, there were no substantial differences between the results, meaning the extra thermal step did not influence the density of the granules.

Table 10: Oxygen induction time of the compounded granules.

Sample	OIT (min)	
	Mean	St. Dev.
G-KM-AO	64.92	(-)
G-KM-NAO	10.00	(-)
G-KM-KM-AO	65.12	(-)
G-KM-CO-AO	31.09	(-)

The OIT results were generated according to the method prescribed in Chapter 7.3, *Characterization of the Pellets*. OIT measures the duration a polymer can resist oxidative degradation. This is clearly seen in the sample without antioxidant (AO), G-KM-NAO, which has a significantly shorter OIT than the other samples with AO. For the samples extruded with the Krauss-Maffei (KM) extruder, the OIT values are similar to each other. However, in the sample extruded with the Coperion (CO), the OIT value is halved compared to the samples extruded only with the KM. Comparing the melt pressures between the two extruders, it is observed that the pressure in the CO is 20 % higher. This can result in more oxidative degradation and thus a lower OIT because, the AO is more consumed in the CO than in the KM.

8.2. Characterization results of the film

The films obtained after film blowing of the various granule grades were characterized for their tensile strength (Table 11), transparency and haze (Table 12), thickness (Table 13) and dart impact strength (Table 14).

Table 11: Tensile properties of the film blown grades

Sample	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elastic modulus (MPa)	Stress @ break (MPa)	Strain @ break (%)
F-KM-C	20.0 ± 1.1	233 ± 4	18.0 ± 1.6	458 ± 17
F-KM-DB	22.4 ± 1.5	262 ± 29	20.9 ± 1.8	511 ± 27
F-KM-KM-C	17.2 ± 0.8	203 ± 11	15.8 ± 1.0	530 ± 35
F-KM-CO-C	21.3 ± 2.7	262 ± 24	19.5 ± 3.2	478 ± 24

The tensile results were generated according to the method prescribed in Chapter 7.5, *Characterization of the Film*. The tensile results do not show a clear trend, and there was no substantial deviation in the tensile properties among the four film-blown samples. However, sample F-KM-DB had the highest tensile strength, elastic modulus and stress at break indicating the best performance.

Table 12: Transparency and haze of the film blown grades.

Sample	Transparency (%)	Haze (%)
F-KM-C	31.8 ± 1.3	72.2 ± 1.1
F-KM-DB	35.9 ± 1.0	64.1 ± 0.7
F-KM-KM-C	31.2 ± 1.6	68.1 ± 1.9
F-KM-CO-C	32.8 ± 1.4	65.5 ± 1.6

The transparency and haze results were generated according to the method prescribed in Chapter 7.5, *Characterization of the Film*. No clear trend was observed, and there were no clear substantial deviations among the four samples. However, sample F-KM-DB had the highest transparency and lowest haze, indicating the best performance.

Table 13: Thickness of the film blown grades.

Sample	Thickness (μm)	
	Mean	St. Dev.
F-KM-C	68	2
F-KM-DB	64	2
F-KM-KM-C	86	3
F-KM-CO-C	77	1

The thickness results were generated according to the method prescribed in Chapter 7.5, *Characterization of the Film*. Samples F-KM-KM-C and F-KM-CO-C were consciously thicker preventing any bubble bursts and ensuring a stable process during film-blowing of the various grades.

Table 14: Dart impact strength of the film blown grades.

Sample	Dart impact ($\text{g}/\mu\text{m}$)	
	Mean	St. Dev.
F-KM-C	2.02	0.05
F-KM-DB	1.86	0.03
F-KM-KM-C	1.85	0.03
F-KM-CO-C	1.22	0.01

The dart impact results were generated according to the method prescribed in Chapter 7.5, *Characterization of the Film*. The sample F-KM-C had the best dart impact result, while the sample F-KM-CO-C performed the poorest.

9. CONCLUSION (EXTRUDER TRIAL)

With the undiluted recyclates (produced using the Loop2 laminates as input waste), film was blown at thickness 60-80 μm . Thinner films of 25-50 μm were not stable in lab-scale processing for this trial. However, achieving thin films was not the purpose of these experiments, rather it was to have a reliable comparison on the effects of scaling the TSE compounding prior to the film blowing.

When comparing the two extruders to give a more in-depth look at the effect of 'scaling up' in extruder size, the 18 mm Coperion and the 25 mm Krauss-Maffei TSE extruders show both differences and similarities in their performance. Tests on the granules showed a decrease in viscosity due to an additional thermal step, which promoted further degradation. In the Coperion extruder, higher melt pressure was measured, resulting in reduced oxidative stability and an Oxidative Induction Time (OIT) that was half of what was measured in the granules from the Krauss-Maffei extruder. However, when evaluating the films produced by various granule grades, no substantial differences or clear trends were identified. The clearest trend observed between the two extruders was the decrease in oxidative stability of the granule grade for the Coperion G-KM-CO-AO.

Overall, while the 18mm Coperion extruder exhibited decreased oxidative stability compared to the 25mm Krauss-Maffei, no other substantial differences were observed in the tests conducted. This suggests that, aside from oxidative stability, both extruders perform comparably in the evaluated tests. Further research could explore additional parameters or conditions to cover other differences between the extruders.

APPENDIX I

Universal extruder screw KraussMaffei ZE 25 (co-rotating, 52L/D, Ø 25 mm):

APPENDIX II

Actual data of the KraussMaffei:

APPENDIX III

Actual data of the Coperion:

APPENDIX IV

Actual data of the Brabender blown film line:

Extruder temperatures:

- Zone 1: 170 °C
- Zone 2: 185 °C
- Zone 3: 200 °C
- Zone 4: 210 °C
- Zone 6: 210 °C
- Zone 7: 210 °C

Extruder speed:

- Screw speed: 40 rpm

Continuous screen changer temperatures:

- Zone 1: 210 °C
- Zone 2: 210 °C
- Zone 3: 210 °C
- Zone 4: 210 °C

Continuous screen changer filter:

- Filter: 80 mesh

Blown film tower setting:

- Height: 2150 mm
- Fan speed: 1700 1/min
- Take-off speed: 3.2 m/min
- Torque: 20 %

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